

Design and Analysis of Series Resonant Converter

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Abstract

Uninterruptible Power Supplies (UPS), which come into play during electricity outages, provide electrical power from an alternative source when grid power is cut off. Batteries, one of the fundamental components of UPS, are pre-charged with grid energy.

In this project, a series resonance converter was used as the power converter. Using the fundamental harmonic approach, methods for determining converter parameters are explained. As a result of the analysis, a series resonance power converter design was carried out for the operating values determined and simulations were made in a computer program with the obtained parameters.

In the study, STM32G474 microcontroller and its special high-resolution timers were used in the control part. The digital control of the circuit was coded using C language. PI method was preferred to obtain constant output voltage. Additionally, various input voltages and load conditions of the circuit were taken into account, and then tests were conducted to evaluate how it Works

Keywords: LLC resonant converter, dc-dc converter, high efficiency, soft and wide frequency range switching, uninterruptible power supply, inverter, PI, STM32G47

Introduction

A series resonance converter was used as the power converter. Using the fundamental harmonic approach, methods for determining converter parameters are explained. As a result of the analysis, a series resonance power converter design was carried out for the operating values determined and simulations were made in a computer program with the obtained parameters.

In this paper, how UPS systems can sustain loads for extended periods during power outages has been investigated. For this purpose, solar energy, one of the renewable energy sources, has been utilized. In the subsequent sections, fundamental information about the general structure of UPS systems has been provided, along with a general overview of solar energy and photovoltaic cells. Within this framework, system design and implementation have been detailed. Additionally, the advantages and disadvantages of UPS systems powered by both conventional means and solar energy have been compared and discussed.

The main focus of the study, the LLC resonant converter, has been thoroughly examined. To understand the operating structure of the converter, it has been modeled using a basic harmonic approach, and its transfer function has been derived. Using the transfer function, the DC characteristic graph has been plotted for different load conditions. Subsequently, the operating principles and regions have been explored, and the equivalent circuit has been provided. Finally, design steps for the LLC resonant converter have been outlined.

Compared to a circuit with open loop control, 150W power, and a separate resonance inductance, the proposed circuit has been observed to offer a wider input voltage range, higher power capability, lower cost, and the ability to regulate voltage with closed-loop control.

The analysis results have shown that theoretical analyses remain valid in practical applications when compared with prototype circuit measurements. Additionally, it has been observed that in designs using high-resolution timers (HRTIM) instead of normal timers, there are several important factors that need to be considered.

Materials and Methods

System Design

In this paper, the system depicted in Figure 1 of the block diagram has been designed. Instead of a PV system module, the system utilizes a DC source and includes a DC-DC converter.

Based on this design, necessary simulations will be conducted, followed by the physical construction of the system. The implemented system will be operated using a digital controller with specified parameters, and the results obtained will be analyzed in detail.

Figure 1. System architecture

Series-Resonance (LLC) Design

In this section, the construction stages of the LLC resonant converter design, which has been previously discussed and analyzed, will be elaborated and implemented according to requirements. The LLC converter will be designed with a full bridge circuit on the primary side and a full bridge rectifier on the secondary side, as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. LLC converter circuit

LLC Operations Regions

Since the gain of the LLC converter is subject to frequency modulation, it can operate in the three different operating modes listed below depending on the input voltage and load current conditions. These modes are illustrated in Figure 3:

Figure 3. LLC resonance converter operation regions

The details of the three modes mentioned above will be explained later in this section; however, the converter has two possible operations, each of which can include one or both of the modes mentioned above, and each mode occurs within the switching cycle as described below.

The power transmission process occurs twice in the switching cycle: Firstly, when the resonance tank is excited with a positive voltage, the current enters resonance in the first half cycle in the positive direction; the equivalent circuit diagram of this mode is shown in Figure 4 Secondly, when the resonance tank is excited with a negative voltage, the current enters resonance in the second half cycle in the negative direction; the equivalent circuit diagram of this mode is shown in Figure 5 below. During power transmission processes, the voltage of the inductor is reflected to be either positive or negative output voltage and the current of the are which even so even M S Thus the had in of that of the even half so of had been of had

Figure 4. When the resonance tank is excited with a positive voltage [13]

Figure 5. When the resonance tank is excited with a negative voltage [13]

The freewheeling process can occur after the power transmission process and only happens when the resonance current reaches the magnetizing current of the transformer. This occurs only when $f_s < f_r$, resulting in the disconnection of the rectifier connection on the secondary side. Therefore, the magnetizing inductor can resonate with the resonant inductor and capacitor. The frequency of this second resonance, especially when $L_m \gg L_r$, is lower than the original resonance frequency f_r . Hence, during the freewheeling process, the change in primary current is limited and can be considered constant for simplicity. The equivalent circuit diagrams of the freewheeling process are shown in the lower figure in each half of the switching cycle.

This section explains the operating modes of the converter and illustrates important waveforms:

- At resonance frequency, when the Q1 MOSFET enters the off state, the resonance current equals the magnetizing current. Therefore, no energy transfer occurs on the secondary side. Simultaneously, the circuit achieves soft switching on the secondary rectifier diodes along with ZVS (Zero Voltage Switching) on the primary side.
- Below resonance frequency, the resonance current (I_r) falls below the magnetizing current before the completion of the switching cycle. Consequently, energy transfer ceases before reaching the resonance frequency. Additionally, the magnetizing current continues on the primary side. In this mode, the converter still achieves ZVS and soft switching for the diodes on the secondary side. This approach effectively reduces the reverse recovery effects of the diodes. Compared to operation above resonance frequency, the current circulating in the primary is higher, leading to increased conduction losses. The circulating current increases as the frequency moves away from resonance.
- Above resonance frequency, the circulating current is lower, resulting in reduced conduction losses. However, in this case, ZCS (Zero Current Switching) does not occur in the secondary rectifier diodes, making it challenging to achieve soft switching.

Figure 6. LLC resonant converter operating regions [infineon Application note]

In Table 1, the requirements for the planned power converter are listed. To create a converter design that meets these requirements, the calculations will be carried out based on the equations specified in the previous sections.

Parameter	Value
Power (W)	270
Output Voltage (V)	380
Input Voltage (V)	50-62
Resonance Frequency (kHz)	66

We proceed with the design as follows: We start the design by calculating the transformer turns ratio and the minimum and maximum voltage gains of the resonant tank.

$$M_{nom}=1 \tag{1}$$

$$N_p/N_s = (V_{in_nom}/V_{out}).M_{nom} = (60 \times 1)/400 = 0.15 \tag{2}$$

$$M_{max} = (V_{in_nom}/V_{in_min}).M_{nom} = (60 \times 1)/50 = 1.2 \tag{3}$$

$$M_{min} = (V_{in_nom}/V_{in_max}).M_{nom} = (33 \times 1)/36 = 0.967 \tag{4}$$

$$Q_{max} \text{ value is } 0.4 \text{ and } m=6.3 \tag{5}$$

Voltage Gain Regulation:

The power is rated at the low input voltages specified in the specifications. Therefore, we need to calculate the maximum Q value at the minimum input voltage condition. Please note that this power rating characteristic is related to the I-V characteristics of the solar panel. (In other application cases where the power rating is the same across the input voltage range, there is only a single Qmax value).

$$Q_{max@vmin}=Q_{max}.V_{in_min}/V_{in_max} = 0.2 \tag{6}$$

Then, we can calculate the maximum gain achieved at the minimum switching frequency. In this case, we can calculate for the Qmax@vmin condition.

$$K_{max}=1.22 \tag{7}$$

$$K_{max}=1.22 > M_{max}=1.833 \tag{8}$$

Resonance values Calculation:

$$R_{ac_min} = (8/\pi^2).(N_p/N_s)^2.(V_{out}^2/P_{o,max}) R_{ac_min}=3.534\Omega \tag{9}$$

$$Q_{max}=0.4=\sqrt{L_r/C_r/R_{ac}} \tag{10}$$

$$f_r=66 \text{ kHz} \tag{11}$$

$$m= 6.3 = (L_r + L_m)/L_r \tag{12}$$

$$L_r = 93 \text{ uH}, L_m = 175\text{uH ve } C_r =500\text{nF} \tag{13}$$

Circuit Modeling

Based on the calculated values and the material selections made, the circuit of the LLC converter was created using the circuit simulation software PSIM.

To design the circuit, the flowchart above was followed, and in the first step, the input and output voltage and the switching frequency of the circuit were determined as shown in Table 1.

Figure 7. LLC converter circuit

The voltage and current waveforms of the MOSFET's drain-source are shown in Figure 8. In this case, it can be observed that the drain-source current is negative when the MOSFET is turned on. This means that the body diode of the MOSFET is conducting, and it can be said that ZVS (Zero Voltage Switching) is achieved.

Figure 8. Vds and Ids curves of the primary high-side MOSFET when $f_s = f_r$

In addition, waveforms of the low-side MOSFET (Q2), taking into account both MOSFETs and gate-source voltages to observe ZVS, are presented in Figure 9. It can be seen that neither MOSFET conducts during dead time, and the tank voltage reaches zero. The voltage is zero when Q2 opens, indicating that ZVS switching occurs.

Figure 9. The gate voltage of the MOSFETs

Figure 10. The VCr and ILr waveforms of the resonant tank

Experimental Results

The designed prototype circuit is shown below. Experimental studies have been conducted on this circuit to validate the design.

Figure 11. Prototype circuit

The experimental setup is shown in Figure 12. The setup includes main inputs of 62V for DC/DC power supplies and 24V for regulators, resistive loads, and measurement tools such as oscilloscope probes and a multimeter.

In the graph in Figure 13, the resonance current and the gate-source voltages on the primary side of the MOSFET are shown at full load. In this case, Zero Voltage Switching (ZVS) is achieved without reset losses due to the tank voltage dropping to zero.

Figure 12. Experimental setup

Figure 13. The waveforms of transition voltages of MOSFETs on the primary side and tank voltage at full load are shown

Figure 14. The waveform of resonance current at full load is shown

Figure 15. Output Power vs. Efficiency graphic

Result

This paper focuses on the analysis of LLC resonant power converters, presenting an investigation into resonant power converters. Based on the conducted analyses, an LLC converter with an output voltage of 380V and a power of 260W has been designed to accommodate varying input voltage ranges. Simulation results of the design and prototype measurement results are also presented in the study.

Using a digital controller and a closed-loop control method with a PI algorithm, output voltage regulation has been achieved. Soft switching has been implemented in the secondary diodes along with the primary switching elements. An efficiency of 94% has been observed under nominal load.

This study shows that compared to an open-loop controlled circuit with a separate resonance inductor and 150W power, the proposed circuit offers advantages such as a wider input voltage range, higher power output, lower cost, and voltage regulation with closed-loop control. Analysis results have demonstrated that theoretical analyses hold validity in practical applications when compared with prototype circuit measurements. Additionally, it has been observed that there are important factors to consider when using High-Resolution Timers (HRTIM) instead of normal timers in designs.

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